

SPH modelling of dissipative sloshing flows under violent vertical harmonic excitation

S. Marrone^a, F. Saltari^b, J. Michel^a, F. Mastroddi^b

^a*CNR - INM, Via di Vallerano 139, 00128, Rome, Italy*

^b*Dept. of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, Sapienza University of Rome, Rome, Italy*

Abstract

In the present work the damping effect of sloshing flows in tanks subjected to vertical harmonic oscillations is modelled through the Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) numerical method. The prediction of energy dissipation in these problems is of interest, among the others, in the aeronautic field to appropriately address sloshing-induced loads on aircraft wings. To this purpose, an enhanced SPH scheme is applied and extensively validated through a comparison with a recent experimental campaign in which a partially filled tank is subjected to harmonic vertical accelerations ranging from 0.25g up to 6g. Conversely to previous works addressing the same phenomenon, in the present work long-time simulations are performed spanning over several periods of oscillations. This approach allows comparing the predicted energy dissipation in terms of averages computed over several tank oscillations, thus providing a robust numerical outcome. The numerical scheme is tested over a large matrix of different frequencies and accelerations covering a wide range of flow regimes and spanning from mildly-deformed free surface to violent shaken flow. Both 2D and 3D numerical frameworks are considered and compared to the experimental reference. It is shown that the 3D solver is able, in most of the cases, to recover the experimental rate of dissipated energy with errors comparable to the intrinsic uncertainties of the problem whereas the 2D solution significantly under-predicts the damping in high-energy sloshing regimes.

Keywords: Sloshing Flows, Dissipative fluid behaviour characterisation, Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics, SPH

*Corresponding author

Email address: salvatore.marrone@cnr.it (S. Marrone)

1. Introduction

Sloshing flows are those occurring when free surface waves are generated inside a tank and caused by any disturbance to partially filled containers. Depending on the type of disturbance and container shape, the liquid surface can experience different types of motion including simple planar, rotational, symmetric, asymmetric, quasi-periodic or chaotic. On the other hand, sloshing flows can be effectively used to dampen the oscillations of a structure. Tuned Liquid Dampers (TLD) exploit the liquid sloshing motion in a tank in order to counteract the external forces and dissipate energy. These dampers are of great interest in many engineering fields, spanning from the control of building stability or the rolling motion of ships in the civil engineering, to aerospace where the suppression of spacecraft instabilities is of fundamental importance during the ascent or landing stages (Graham and Rodriguez (1952); Abramson (1966)).

From the physical point of view, the study and prediction of the energy dissipation induced by a free-surface flow is generally arduous, especially in presence of wave breaking. Perlin et al. (2013) presented a review of studies dedicated to the dissipation caused by wave breaking. From a numerical point of view, several methods have been used to evaluate energy dissipation in breaking waves. As far as SPH modelling of sloshing flows is concerned, in Bouscasse et al. (2014a) and Bouscasse et al. (2014b) a dynamical system involving a driven pendulum filled with liquid was studied experimentally and numerically by Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH), focusing on the mechanical energy dissipation of the system.

Recently, kerosene containers placed inside aircraft wings have received attention as a complex industrial sloshing problem (Gambioli et al. (2019)). During flight, sudden strong gusts accelerate the wing tips up to values of 10g, which results in sloshing amplitudes comparable to the tank dimensions and frequencies higher than 5 Hz (see Gambioli and Malan (2017)). The resulting flow is significantly different from typical sloshing flows: the fuel is continuously broken into several jets and drops, whilst violently slamming alternately upward and downward against the tank walls. This complex fluid motion plays a key role on the damping of the wing vibrations as demonstrated in experimental campaigns carried out within the EU H2020 project “SLOWD” (Gambioli et al. (2020); Constantin et al. (2021); De Courcy et al. (2021)).

In Marrone et al. (2021b,a); Calderon-Sanchez et al. (2021), such a violent flow has been numerically studied by reproducing the experiments in Martinez-

Carrascal and González-Gutiérrez (2021) in which a partially filled tank was subjected to a decaying vertical oscillating motion. The rapidly decaying flow motion on one hand allows one to perform short time simulations but, on the other hand, introduces difficulties in assessing the energy dissipation without solving the full fluid-structure interaction problem (for more details see Marrone et al. (2021a)).

In order to overcome those limitations, in the present work the experiments described in Saltari et al. (2022a) are considered. In that experimental campaign a purely harmonic vertical motion is imposed on a partially filled tank with peak accelerations up to $6g$. The SPH method is used to numerically reproduce the resulting flow with the aim of providing a sound numerical analysis and extending the findings in Saltari et al. (2022a). Conversely to the experiments in Martínez-Carrascal and González-Gutiérrez (2021), in the present approach the tank motion is imposed, thus avoiding the need to solve the complex fluid-structure interaction. Further, the use of harmonic motions makes possible to evaluate energy dissipation as an average values over several oscillation cycles, providing a robust and reliable validation of the adopted SPH solver for this kind of problem. A large test case matrix spanning several motion frequencies and amplitudes is considered and the relevance of aspects such as surface tension and 3D effects are analysed and discussed.

Experimental validation of the proposed scheme enables its use to gather data for training reduced-order models for sloshing described in De Courcy et al. (2021); Saltari et al. (2022b); Pizzoli et al. (2023) that can be integrated into dynamic wing response simulations. The synthesis of such response operators can then be performed regardless of the shape and size of the tank and the type of motion to be imposed on the tank, overcoming the limitations of experimental analysis.

2. Reference experimental campaign

The experimental testbed of the present analysis was described in detail in Saltari et al. (2022a) and is briefly recalled here. It consists of a box tank made in Plexiglass with a height of $h = 27.2$ mm and base of sides $l_1 = 117.2$ mm and $l_2 = 78.0$, mm. A picture of the box is shown in left plot of figure 1. The dimensions are chosen in order to be able to trigger fluid slamming with the tank ceiling after an initial transient stage.

The tank was placed over a controlled electrodynamic shaker able to impose vertical sinusoidal displacement from a lower frequency of 5 Hz and able to reach

25 mm peak-to-peak displacement amplitude. The dynamic load at the interface between shaker and tank was measured by two PCB 208C03 load cells, placed in the middle of the long side of the tank base. Sloshing forces were determined by summation of two load cell signals, from which the inertial force of the non liquid mass upon the load cells must be subtracted. The system was also equipped with two redundant PCB 352C22 accelerometers placed at the opposite corners of the tank upper closing side and with a control accelerometer used by the shaker sine-sweep controller. The comparison between the data of the accelerometer used for sine-sweep control and the other two over the tank roof confirmed the considered experimental testbed rigidly behaved throughout the tests carried out.

The identification of the sloshing forces was carried out under sine-sweep excitation regime at constant acceleration. The curves showed in figure 2 illustrate the paths of the frequency-amplitude pairs run through the sine-sweep tests. The arrows indicate the direction followed by the frequency sweep during the test. The minimum (0.25 g) and maximum (6 g) iso-acceleration curves therefore define the domain where the energy dissipated by the fluid inside the tank is experimentally identified. The frequency sweep rate is 0.5 octave per second meaning that the frequency sweeps from 5 Hz to 20 Hz in 240 s . This time is sufficiently long with respect to the period associated to the related oscillations to consider negligible the transient from a state to another. The tests were performed at different values of accelerations but in the present work only excitations ranging from 1.5 g to 6.0 g are considered, as mostly representative of sloshing-induced damping in aircraft wings (see Gambioli et al. (2019); Pagliaroli et al. (2022)). It is worth to notice that the frequency-amplitude paths of higher acceleration tests in figure 2 not necessarily follow iso-acceleration curves since the electromechanical shaker is limited in providing at most 12.5 mm of displacement amplitude.

Right plot of figure 1 provides a snapshot of flow evolution for the test at $a_0 = 3.0g$ of acceleration amplitude, when the frequency of the oscillation is $f = 13Hz$. The method developed in Saltari et al. (2022a) allowed to identify the energy dissipated by the sloshing fluid for all the frequency-amplitude pairs covered by the paths in figure 2.

3. Governing equations

In the present work both two-dimensional and three-dimensional frameworks are considered and the relevance of this aspect on the numerical outcome is addressed in the numerical study. The liquid domain Ω is bounded by the tank walls $\partial\Omega_B$ and the free surface $\partial\Omega_F$. Following the works in Bouscasse et al.

Figure 1: Experimental set up and snapshot of the sloshing flow at $a_0 = 1.5g$, $f = 9Hz$.

Figure 2: Frequency-acceleration amplitude pairs spanned during different sine sweep tests to identify a dissipated energy map.

(2014b); Marrone et al. (2016a, 2021b), only the liquid phase is considered in the present study. The air phase, indeed, has only a minor role in the energy dissipation even though it can play a key role in local features of the flow, such as air-cushioning effects during impacts. In the present work a further validation of the appropriateness of the single-phase approximation for the evaluation of energy dissipation in sloshing flows is provided. The flow evolution is governed by the Navier-Stokes equations written for a weakly-compressible fluid:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{D\rho}{Dt} = -\rho \operatorname{div}(\mathbf{u}), & \frac{D\mathbf{u}}{Dt} = \mathbf{g} + \frac{\operatorname{div}(\mathbb{T})}{\rho} \\ \frac{De}{Dt} = \frac{\mathbb{T} : \mathbb{D}}{\rho}, & \frac{D\mathbf{r}}{Dt} = \mathbf{u}, \quad p = f(\rho) \end{cases}$$

where D/Dt represents the Lagrangian derivative, \mathbf{u} the flow velocity, \mathbf{r} the position of the material points, ρ the fluid density, e the specific internal energy, \mathbb{T} the stress tensor, \mathbb{D} the rate of strain tensor and \mathbf{g} the gravitational acceleration. The thermal conductivity is neglected and the liquid is assumed to be Newtonian, *i.e.* $\mathbb{T} = [-p + \lambda \operatorname{div}(\mathbf{u})] + 2\mu\mathbb{D}$. Differently from Marrone et al. (2021b), in the present work the surface tension is included since Weber number can be as small as $We = O(10)$ for the test cases characterised by low acceleration and high frequency.

Sloshing flows can be addressed by solving system (1) either in an inertial frame of reference, for which the tank motion is also solved, or in a non-inertial frame of reference, that is the frame moving with the tank. Even though this choice does not affect the evaluation of the energy dissipated by the fluid, from a numerical point of view there are pros and cons when choosing the reference to adopt. In fact, while the use of an inertial frame of reference is generally preferred when complex body motions are considered, the use of the non-inertial frame of reference allows a more precise control of the solution: i) from an algorithmic point of view as it is simpler to implement and verify with respect to a moving body; ii) with respect to the accuracy of the energy budget, as additional issues arise when evaluating the contribution of ghost fluid to the energy budget for a moving body (see Cercos-Pita et al. (2017)). In the present work, the non-inertial frame of reference is, thus, used. To this end a volume force \mathbf{f}_{NI} is introduced in the momentum equation to take into account accelerations of the frame of reference due to the moving tank.

Due to the weakly-compressibility assumption, the liquid is treated as a barotropic medium and its pressure p is assumed to depend only on the density. Furthermore, since density variation are assumed to be small, a simple linear

equation of state can be adopted: $p = c_0^2 (\rho - \rho_0)$ where c_0 is a constant speed of sound of the liquid and ρ_0 is the density at the free-surface (where p is assumed to be equal to zero). Since the time step depends upon the choice of c_0 , the latter is always set lower than its physical counterpart (in the present work, about two orders of magnitude lower) in order to save CPU resources. In particular, c_0 shall be selected according to the following requirements:

$$c_0 \geq 10 \max\left(U_{max}, \sqrt{(\Delta p)_{max}/\rho}\right), \quad (1)$$

where U_{max} and $(\Delta p)_{max}$ stand respectively for the expected maximum velocity and pressure variation within the fluid domain. The above constraint must be enforced in order to guarantee the weakly-compressible regime, that is, fluid density variations smaller than 1%. As discussed in Marrone et al. (2015) and in Meringolo et al. (2017), in the weakly-compressible regime the energy dissipation linked to the water impacts using eq. (1) is consistent with the one predicted by incompressible flow models.

4. Numerical scheme

In this section the adopted SPH numerical model adopted is briefly described, and for specific details the interested reader is referred to the articles mentioned below. The governing equations (1) are discretized according to the Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics numerical approach. The numerical diffusive terms are obtained by means of Riemann solver, and the technique derived in Parshikov and Medin (2002) and further discussed in Michel et al. (2023) is used. A Particle Shifting Technique (PST) is used to obtain regular particle distributions and consequently accurate SPH interpolations. The PST velocity $\delta \mathbf{u}$ derived in Michel et al. (2022b) and further improved in Michel et al. (2023) is considered and taken into account within the continuity and momentum equations through the quasi-Lagrangian model derived in Sun et al. (2019), *i.e.* using the quasi-Lagrangian time derivative $\frac{d(\bullet)}{dt} = \frac{D(\bullet)}{dt} + \nabla(\bullet) \cdot \delta \mathbf{u}$. The mass m_i of the i -th particle is assumed to be constant during its motion. The solid boundary conditions are enforced using the classical ghost technique Colagrossi and Landrini (2003).

Finally the scheme reads:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{d\rho_i}{dt} = -\rho_i \langle \text{div}(\mathbf{u}_i) \rangle - \rho_i \langle \text{div}(\delta\mathbf{u}_i) \rangle + \langle \text{div}(\rho_i \delta\mathbf{u}_i) \rangle + \Theta_{i,Rie}^\rho \\ m_i \frac{d(\mathbf{u}_i)}{dt} = -V_i \langle \nabla P_i \rangle + V_i \langle \text{div}(\rho_i \mathbf{u}_i \otimes \delta\mathbf{u}_i) \rangle + \Theta_{i,Rie}^u + m_i \mathbf{f}_i + \mathbf{F}_i^v + \mathbf{F}_i^\sigma \\ \frac{d\mathbf{r}_i}{dt} = \mathbf{u}_i + \delta\mathbf{u}_i, \quad \rho_i(t) = m_i / V_i(t), \quad p = c_0^2(\rho - \rho_0), \end{array} \right. \quad (2)$$

where the spatial differential operators are approximated by:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \text{div}(\mathbf{u}_i) \rangle &= \sum_j (\mathbf{u}_j - \mathbf{u}_i) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \quad ; \quad \langle \text{div}(\delta\mathbf{u}_i) \rangle = \sum_j (\delta\mathbf{u}_j - \delta\mathbf{u}_i) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \\ \langle \text{div}(\rho_i \delta\mathbf{u}_i) \rangle &= \sum_j (\rho_i \delta\mathbf{u}_i + \rho_j \delta\mathbf{u}_j) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \quad ; \quad \langle \nabla P_i \rangle = \sum_j (P_i + P_j) \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \\ \langle \text{div}(\rho_i \mathbf{u}_i \otimes \delta\mathbf{u}_i) \rangle &= \sum_j (\rho_i \mathbf{u}_i \otimes \delta\mathbf{u}_i + \rho_j \mathbf{u}_j \otimes \delta\mathbf{u}_j) \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j, \end{aligned}$$

in which the index i refers to the considered particle and j refers to neighbour particles of i . The particles are set initially on a Cartesian lattice with spacing Δx , and hence, the volumes V_i are initially evaluated as Δx^2 and Δx^3 , respectively in 2D and in 3D. W is the kernel function which, in the present work, is a C^2 -Wendland kernel Wendland (1995). The kernel radius R is equal to $4\Delta x$ and $2.7\Delta x$, respectively in 2D and in 3D.

The numerical diffusive terms $\Theta_{i,Rie}^\rho$ and $\Theta_{i,Rie}^u$ are:

$$\begin{aligned} \Theta_{i,Rie}^\rho &= \frac{1}{\rho_i} \sum_j \left[\left(\mathbf{u}_i + \mathbf{u}_j - 2 \frac{\rho_R \mathbf{u}_R + \rho_L \mathbf{u}_L}{\rho_R + \rho_L} \right) \cdot \mathbf{n}_{ij} + 2 \frac{P_R - P_L}{c_0 (\rho_R + \rho_L)} \right] \mathbf{n}_{ij} \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j, \\ \Theta_{i,Rie}^u &= V_i \sum_j \left[P_i + P_j - 2 \frac{\rho_R P_L + \rho_L P_R - c_0 \rho_R \rho_L (\mathbf{u}_R - \mathbf{u}_L) \cdot \mathbf{n}_{ij}}{\rho_R + \rho_L} \right] \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j, \end{aligned}$$

where the subscripts \cdot_L and \cdot_R stand for the reconstructed variables on each part of the interface between particles i and j .

The vector \mathbf{F}_i^v and \mathbf{F}_i^σ are the forces due to viscosity and surface tension acting on the particle i . The viscous effects are modelled using the classical formulation by Monaghan and Gingold (1983). The surface tension model presented in Vergnaud et al. (2022) is adopted since it has proved to be accurate even in single-phase

approximation. The viscous force \mathbf{F}^v is expressed as:

$$\mathbf{F}_i^v = K \sum_j \mu \frac{(\mathbf{u}_j - \mathbf{u}_i) \cdot (\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i)}{\|\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i\|^2} \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j V_i \quad (3)$$

where $K = 2(n + 2)$ being n is the number of spatial dimensions and μ is the fluid viscosity. The surface tension force \mathbf{F}^σ is written in the form of a continuous surface force:

$$\mathbf{F}_i^\sigma = -\sigma \kappa_i \mathbf{n}_i \delta_{\Sigma,i} V_i \quad (4)$$

where σ is the surface tension coefficient, κ the curvature at the interface, \mathbf{n}_i the unit vector normal to the interface and $\delta_{\Sigma,i}$ an interfacial function.

Finally, \mathbf{f}_i stands for the external volume forces, and contains both the gravity component \mathbf{g} and the non-inertial component \mathbf{f}_{NI} . In present work \mathbf{f}_{NI} is used to enforce the acceleration of frame of reference and, thus, is equal (with opposed sign) to the tank acceleration \mathbf{a}_{tank} .

The scheme is then integrated in time through a 4th-order Runge-Kutta scheme, with the following CFL condition:

$$\Delta t = \min \left[\alpha_h \frac{R}{c_0}, \alpha_v \frac{R^2}{\nu}, \alpha_a \min_i \sqrt{\frac{R}{a_i}}, \alpha_{ST} \min_i \sqrt{\frac{\rho_i R^2}{2\pi\sigma|\kappa_i|}}, \alpha_{ALE} \min_i \sqrt{\frac{R}{|\text{div}(\mathbf{u}_i \otimes \delta \mathbf{u}_i)|}} \right] \quad (5)$$

where the values $\alpha_h = 0.375$, $\alpha_v = 0.025$, $\alpha_{ST} = 0.05$, $\alpha_a = 0.18$ and $\alpha_{ALE} = 0.012$ are used in the present paper. Note that, while first four terms in (5) are standard, the last one is derived following the idea in Loubère et al. (2010) where a CFL condition is introduced in Finite Volume ALE scheme to control large volume changes due to mesh deformation. In the present work this further CFL condition was needed to control the PST term in the momentum equation in most violent cases. It was observed, indeed, that without this additional CFL condition, issues regarding the overall volume occupied by the fluid may occur in such simulations. Thanks to its introduction the relative volume changes are limited to a maximum of about 5% with little influence on the overall simulation cost, even though the time step reduction can reach up to one third of the acoustic constraint.

5. Considerations on the energy dissipation

Following the analysis performed in Marrone et al. (2021b) and in Michel et al. (2023), the energy balance for the particle system (2) is reported below. For the sake of brevity, only the main terms are briefly discussed in this section.

The SPH energy balance can be written as:

$$\dot{\mathcal{E}}_M + \dot{\mathcal{E}}_C + \dot{\mathcal{E}}_\sigma = \mathcal{P}_V + \mathcal{P}_N + \mathcal{P}_{NF} \quad (6)$$

where \mathcal{E}_M is the mechanical energy of the particle system, formed by kinetic energy \mathcal{E}_K and potential energy \mathcal{E}_P , for the present work expressed as:

$$\mathcal{E}_K = \frac{1}{2} \sum_i m_i \|\mathbf{u}_i\|^2; \quad \mathcal{E}_P = - \sum_i m_i (\mathbf{g} \cdot \mathbf{r}_i).$$

Within the weakly compressible regime, the elastic energy term \mathcal{E}_C is generally negligible in the energy balance; hence it is not considered in the following discussion. \mathcal{E}_σ is the surface energy associated to the liquid surface tension and is equal to $\mathcal{E}_\sigma = \sigma S$, S being the area of the liquid free surface. The term \mathcal{P}_{NF} is the power produced by non-inertial forces and is equal to

$$\mathcal{P}_{NF} = \sum_i m_i (\mathbf{f}_{NI} \cdot \mathbf{u}_i).$$

The term \mathcal{P}_V refers to the power related to the viscous forces and the term \mathcal{P}_N takes into account the effect of the numerical diffusion related to Particle Shifting terms and Riemann stabilization terms (see Michel et al. (2023) for more details). The energy dissipated by the fluid, \mathcal{E}_{diss} , can be obtained by integrating in time eq. (6):

$$\begin{cases} \mathcal{E}_{tot}(t) - \mathcal{E}_{tot}(t_0) = \mathcal{E}_{diss}(t) + \mathcal{W}_{NF}(t) \\ \mathcal{W}_{NF}(t) := \int_{t_0}^t \mathcal{P}_{NF} d\tau, \quad \mathcal{E}_{diss}(t) := \int_{t_0}^t \mathcal{P}_V + \mathcal{P}_N d\tau \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

where $\mathcal{E}_{tot} = \mathcal{E}_M + \mathcal{E}_\sigma$ and t_0 is the initial time instant of the simulation. Note that in purely periodic motions, such as the ones considered in the present work, eq. (7) can be simplified as:

$$- [\mathcal{W}_{NF}(t+T) - \mathcal{W}_{NF}(t)] \simeq \mathcal{E}_{diss}(t+T) - \mathcal{E}_{diss}(t). \quad (8)$$

When the tank is subjected to periodic forced motions the resulting flow is quasi-periodic as a turbulent chaotic perturbation is superimposed to the purely periodic flow component. In this flow regime the differences in mechanical energy between two periods are null in average and, thus, the approximation in eq. (8) holds true.

The appropriateness of this approximation is shown in section 6 figure 3 and is exploited for the evaluation of the average dissipated energy per motion cycle.

Expression in eq. (8) can be directly related to the work done by external forces on the tank. In the experiments by Saltari et al. (2022a) the measured forces on the tank are, indeed, used to evaluate the energy dissipation by the liquid sloshing using the following expression:

$$\begin{cases} - [\mathcal{W}_{ext}(t+T) - \mathcal{W}_{ext}(t)] \simeq \mathcal{E}_{diss}(t+T) - \mathcal{E}_{diss}(t) \\ \mathcal{W}_{ext}(t) := \int_{t_0}^t \mathbf{F}_{slo} \cdot \mathbf{u}_{tank} d\tau \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

where \mathbf{F}_{slo} are the measured sloshing forces in the experiment and \mathbf{u}_{tank} is the tank velocity. The above expression too is valid as far as a quasi-periodic flow regime is established. In fact, as shown in Marrone et al. (2021b) $\mathcal{W}_{ext} \neq \mathcal{W}_{NF}$ when the flow is not periodic.

5.1. Sloshing-effective mass fraction

Characterizing the energy dissipated by sloshing forces is important for quantifying the level of damping introduced into the response of a vibrating structure containing the tank (see Saltari et al. (2022b)). This type of dissipation is generated by the phase shift between the sloshing forces and the vertical tank motion. However, energy dissipation is not the only effect given by sloshing forces. Thinking of a structure containing a tank with a liquid considered as *frozen*, the latter behaves as a ballast generating inertia affecting the dynamic response of the structure and its natural frequencies. When the fluid is considered as such, its centre of mass tends to move in counterphase with respect to the tank walls in an absolute reference system, thus generating a reduction in apparent mass (from a structural point of view). This effect results in a change in the structural response frequencies that are a function of the amplitude and the excitation frequency.

According to Saltari et al. (2022b), the variation of the *apparent mass*, hereafter denoted sloshing-effective mass fraction β , can be identified by assuming the linear approximation of the dynamic sloshing force (removing the effects of the superharmonics) and performing the ratio between the Fourier transform of the dynamic sloshing force and the related frozen liquid model force:

$$\beta = \mathcal{R} \left[\frac{\tilde{\mathbf{F}}_{slo}(\omega_0) \cdot \mathbf{k}}{m \tilde{\mathbf{a}}_{tank}(\omega_0) \cdot \mathbf{k}} \right] - 1 \quad (10)$$

where $\tilde{\cdot}$ and $\mathcal{R}[\cdot]$ are used, respectively, to represent the Fourier transform and the real part, \mathbf{k} is the vertical unit vector and m is the mass of the liquid. This quantity is generally negative, meaning that the inertial contribution of the liquid is lower than that of the *frozen* fluid model. The sloshing-effective mass fraction represents a further signature of the vertical sloshing force and in section 6.3 it is used to compare the capability of the considered numerical scheme to predict the sloshing behaviour.

6. Numerical results

In this section the SPH simulations of the experimental test cases described in section 2 are presented. We chose not to perform the numerical simulation of the whole experimental sine-sweep tests, which would result in very large CPU costs. Instead, we preferred to perform several single-frequency periodic simulations in order to explore the same acceleration-frequency space as shown in figure 2. In the non-inertial frame of reference adopted in the present work, a sinusoidal volume force $\mathbf{f}_{NI} = a_0 \cos(\omega_0 t) \mathbf{k}$ corresponding to the frequency, f , and acceleration amplitude, a_0 , of each specific test case is applied.

The dissipated energy in the experiment was measured through the evaluation of the work done by external forces \mathcal{W}_{ext} following eq. (9) whereas in the simulation it is more convenient to directly evaluate it integrating non-inertial forces as in eq. (8). In order to show justify this procedure. in figure 3 the time evolution of the different terms of eq. (7) are reported for the case at $a_0 = 3g$ and $f = 13Hz$. At the beginning of the simulation, approximately at $t/T = 8$ when the sloshing flow is triggered (see section 6.1 for more details), the flow energy \mathcal{E}_{tot} increases substantially due to an increase of the flow kinetic energy. This increase of the fluid stored energy corresponds to the work done by non-inertial forces, \mathcal{W}_{NF} .

After this initial stage, the flow rapidly reaches a quasi-periodic regime and \mathcal{E}_{tot} oscillates around a constant value for the remaining part of the simulation. During this stage energy is dissipated as a result of the violent sloshing flow developed in the tank. Consequently, \mathcal{W}_{NF} is entirely transferred into dissipated energy \mathcal{E}_{diss} during each oscillation cycle. This is clear from figure 3 where \mathcal{W}_{NF} and \mathcal{E}_{diss} are characterised by parallel paths, their difference being equal to \mathcal{E}_{tot} . This result motivates the evaluation of the dissipated energy as defined in eq. (8).

The average values of the energy dissipated per cycle, $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{diss}$ are evaluated from the average work done by non-inertial forces in $N_P = 50$ periods for 2D simulations and $N_P = 20$ periods for 3D ones. This difference between 2D and 3D is due to

Figure 3: Comparison of energy terms \mathcal{W}_{NF} , \mathcal{E}_{diss} and \mathcal{E}_{tot} (see eq. (7) and eq. (8)).

the different convergence behaviour of the average with the number of periods: 2D simulations required a larger number of oscillations to get a fully converged statistics. This aspect is due to the higher irregularity of the flow obtained in 2D and is described in detail in section 6.3. In any case, this number of periods is enough for comparison with experiments as in Saltari et al. (2022a) $N_P = 10$ was adopted.

It is important to note that the time history considered for the evaluation of $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{diss}$ does not take into account the initial transient stage of the simulation when the first flow impacts take place. This transient stage is different for each test condition and is conservatively estimated as the first $N_{P0} = 15$ periods from the beginning of the simulation. For the test cases characterised by weaker dynamics, the onset of the flow instability is accelerated by initially applying a perturbation at the free surface as done in Marrone et al. (2021a). Finally, $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{diss}$ is evaluated as:

$$\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{diss} = -\frac{1}{N_P} \sum_{k=N_{P0}}^{N_P+N_{P0}} \int_{kT}^{(k+1)T} \mathcal{P}_{NF} d\tau = -\frac{1}{N_P} [\mathcal{W}_{NF}(t_f) - \mathcal{W}_{NF}(t_i)]$$

where $t_f = (N_P + N_{P0})T$ and $t_i = N_{P0}T$. The related standard deviation, $\sigma_{\mathcal{E}}$, is computed as follows:

$$\sigma_{\mathcal{E}} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N_P} \sum_{k=N_{P0}}^{N_P+N_{P0}} \left(\int_{kT}^{(k+1)T} \mathcal{P}_{NF} d\tau - \bar{\mathcal{E}}_{diss} \right)^2}$$

In figure 4 an overview of all the considered test conditions is represented in the acceleration-frequency diagram. The acceleration amplitude, a_0 , ranges from 1.5g up to 6g. In the same figure the contour map of the energy dissipated in the experiment (see Saltari et al. (2022a)) is represented in order to show the distribution of most violent test cases. The tank filling ratio is 50%, corresponding to a water depth $H = 13.5\text{mm}$ and mass of the liquid $m = 0.123\text{kg}$.

The considered physical parameters for the fluid are those for water at 25° , i.e. density $\rho = 998 \text{ kg / m}^3$, dynamic viscosity $\mu = 8.9 \times 10^{-4} \text{ Pa} \cdot \text{s}$ and surface tension $\gamma = 72 \times 10^{-3} \text{ N/m}$. The flow Reynolds number is defined as $\text{Re} = \frac{\rho U H}{\mu}$ where the reference velocity is $U = a_0 / \omega_0$ with $\omega_0 = 2\pi / T$; Re ranges between 2000 and 10000 in test matrix of figure 4. For these values viscous effects are

Figure 4: Overview of the test-case matrix of the performed numerical simulations: green dots represent the test conditions considered for the 3D SPH simulations whereas red diamonds are representative of 2D simulations. The colour map represent the experimental average dissipated energy as a function of acceleration amplitude and frequency.

significant and boundary layer influence is not negligible. Thus, no-slip conditions are enforced at the solid walls.

6.1. Description of the flow evolution

An example of the 2D flow evolution is reported in figure 5 where the first impact against the tank ceiling for the case at $a_0 = 3.0g$, $f = 13Hz$ is shown. The fluid hit the ceiling after about 8 oscillation periods as the amplitude of the oscillation gradually increases. The impact is the result of the progressive amplification of a standing wave that establishes at the beginning of the simulation forced by the oscillating vertical acceleration (top plot of figure 5). After the impact against the tank ceiling the liquid jets expand over the wall (second plot of figure 5) and, then, new descending jets are generated as a result of the thin converging liquid layers. The surface tension acting at this length scale produces evident drops at the tip of the fluid jets. These drops impact against the fluid below and trigger a much larger ejection of liquid jets forced by the downward tank acceleration (third and fourth plots of figure 5). The following evolution is a sort of sloshing flow which in Marrone et al. (2021b) was denoted as "shaken flow". The fluid alternatively slams against the ceiling and the floor of the tank with production of several vortical structures and consequent dissipation of energy.

A similar initial evolution is reproduced also in 3D simulations. This is described in figure 6 where the first impact against the ceiling is shown. Remarkably, the flow develops through three uprising jets impacting against the ceiling and forming a thin liquid layer expanding on the wall, similarly to what observed in the experiments for the same oscillation frequency (see bottom plot of figure 6) Benjamin et al. (1954) illustrates that sloshing modes having natural frequency close to half the excitation frequency are likely to develop parametric instability when the tank is set on vertical motion. Considering the geometry of the tank, the sloshing mode with 6 half-waves (3 fingers) - as reported in Saltari et al. (2022a) - is the one closest to having frequency close to half of $13H$. It is also worth noting that in the 3D case the flow instability occurs earlier with respect to the 2D one: this is expected as the additional degree of freedom allows for a faster development of the instability. In fact, the higher free-surface modal density featured by the 3D framework results in an increased likelihood of triggering flow instabilities. The evolution which follows the first impact is similar to the two-dimensional one but less regular and more complex in terms of topology of the free surface.

In order to provide a picture of the several flow regimes obtained for the different test conditions, in figure 7 the non-dimensional vorticity field for four different cases is shown. Test cases with nominal acceleration values equal to $a_0 = 1.5g$

Figure 5: Initial evolution of the 2D simulation for the case at $a_0 = 3.0g, f = 13\text{Hz}$. Colors refer to the non-dimensional vorticity $\nabla \times \mathbf{u} / \omega_0$

Figure 6: Top and middle plots: initial evolution of the 3D simulation for the case at $a_0 = 3.0g$, $f = 13Hz$. Bottom plot: snapshot of the flow evolution in the experiments highlighting three uprising jets impacting against the tank ceiling.

Figure 7: Comparison of the non-dimensional vorticity field obtained in 2D simulations for different flow conditions at the same time instant. Top-left plot $a_0 = 1.5g, f = 9Hz$; top-right plot $a_0 = 1.5g, f = 13Hz$; bottom-left plot $a_0 = 3.0g, f = 9Hz$; bottom-right plot $a_0 = 3.0g, f = 13Hz$.

and $a_0 = 3.0g$ and frequencies equal to $f = 9Hz$ and $f = 13Hz$ are considered. The different flow configurations are taken at the same time instant. The case characterised by lowest value of U , corresponding to small nominal kinetic energy of the tank, is the case at $a_0 = 1.5g$, $f = 13Hz$. At test conditions the flow exhibits very few vortex structures and a rather compact fluid configuration. Further, fluid displacements occur only in the form of thin jets flowing towards and from the ceiling. The case at $a_0 = 1.5g$, $f = 9Hz$, which corresponds to a larger value of U , has a much richer distribution of vortices with larger intensity, which are caused by a larger amount of liquid impacting against the tank ceiling and consequent more intense breaking events.

This trend is confirmed in both cases at $a_0 = 3.0g$ for which the associated values of U are even higher. The fluid configurations are characterised by large fragmentation and a complex vorticity field due to the repeated flow impacts occurring during each period. This high-vorticity content is related to high levels of energy dissipation by viscosity and, as discussed in Saltari et al. (2022a), this behaviour straightforwardly follows the fact that higher values of the tank kinetic energy are associated to higher energy dissipation by the fluid.

In order to better describe the relation between fluid kinetic energy and energy dissipation, in figure 8 the time history of \mathcal{E}_K , \mathcal{E}_P and \mathcal{P}_{NF} is reported for three periods of oscillation in the quasi-periodic flow regime. The \mathcal{E}_K curve has two local maxima for each period: the first and higher peak (label a) corresponds to the fluid falling down from the ceiling towards the floor of the tank; the following second peak (label b), on the contrary is representative of fluid ejected towards the ceiling. Those two \mathcal{E}_K peaks are immediately followed by, respectively, a local minimum and a local maximum of the potential energy \mathcal{E}_P . The latter is indicated by label c in figure 8 where the maximum of \mathcal{E}_P corresponds to the minimum of \mathcal{E}_K , that is, the lowest value of the fluid kinetic energy is attained after the impact against the tank ceiling takes place. It is worth reminding that all these quantities are referred to a frame of reference moving with the tank.

As for \mathcal{P}_{NF} , the local minima, *i.e.* when energy dissipation rate is larger, take place between a minimum and a maximum of \mathcal{E}_P . This means that most of the energy is dissipated either when fluid is flowing towards the ceiling or when it is falling back towards the floor. During those stages multiple impacts occur and part of the kinetic energy is dissipated through vorticity. Therefore, it naturally follows that the higher the kinetic energy content of the fluid, the higher the dissipated energy during impacts.

Figure 8: Time history of the fluid kinetic energy (black solid line) \mathcal{E}_K , potential energy (grey dashed line), \mathcal{E}_P , and power associated to non-inertial forces (red solid line), \mathcal{P}_{NF} , for three oscillation cycles of the 3D simulation at $a_0 = 3.0g$ and $f = 13Hz$.

6.2. Convergence analysis

In order to choose the discretization to adopt and assess the dependency of the results on the spatial resolution, in figures 9 and 10 the results of the convergence study for the case $a_0 = 3.0g$, $f = 13Hz$, are reported. For the convergence analysis 2D simulations are performed with resolutions $H/\Delta x = [12, 25, 50, 100, 200]$ (ratio 2 between two consecutive resolutions) whereas 3D simulations are performed with resolutions $H/\Delta x = [13, 16, 20, 25, 31]$ (ratio 1.25 between two consecutive resolutions). In the left plot of figures 9 and 10 the different time evolution of \mathcal{E}_{diss} are reported. For the ease of visualisation the initial time is taken as the time when the flow instability is triggered. The steepness of the energy curves, i.e. the energy dissipated per period, is evidently converging as the resolution is increased.

In right plots of the same figures only the computed values of $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{diss}$ and the related standard deviation $\sigma_{\mathcal{E}}$ are shown as a function of the particle resolution. A convergent value of $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{diss}$ is observed for both the average and standard deviation of the dissipated energy per cycle in both 2D and 3D cases (as mentioned above, each average is computed discarding the first 15 periods of the entire time history). In the latter case, the results is still not fully converged due to the limitations of CPU resources required. However, it should be noted that this result is all but trivial given the complexity of the considered flow.

The rate of convergence varies with the resolution and from 2D and 3D frameworks: in 2D it is between 1 and 3 whereas in 3D it oscillates around 1. Other

Figure 9: Convergence analysis for the case $a_0 = 3.0g$, $f = 13Hz$ in 2D simulations. Left plot: time evolution of the dissipated energy for five different resolutions, namely $H/\Delta x = [12, 25, 50, 100, 200]$. Right plot: average dissipated energy per cycle, $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{diss}$, and standard deviation $\sigma_{\mathcal{E}}$ as a function of the spatial resolution.

Figure 10: Convergence analysis for the case $a_0 = 3.0g$, $f = 13Hz$ in 3D simulations. Left plot: time evolution of the dissipated energy for five different resolutions, namely $H/\Delta x = [13, 16, 20, 25, 31]$. Right plot: average dissipated energy per cycle, $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{diss}$, and standard deviation $\sigma_{\mathcal{E}}$ as a function of the spatial resolution.

test conditions are also considered for the convergence study (see Marrone et al.

(2022) for more details) which, for the sake of conciseness, are not reported here. It is worth noting that a convergent result is achieved for all the studied cases. For this reason the whole test-case matrix is performed using the spatial resolution $H/\Delta x = 100$ for 2D and $H/\Delta x = 25$ for 3D. It is worth remarking that even though the resolution adopted for the 3D case is much coarser with respect to the 2D one, the solution obtained is close to convergence. This is not the case when adopting the same resolution in 2D. This aspect is also quite clear in the left plots of figures 9 and 10: 2D energy evolution has a larger variability along the time history with respect to 2D for the same spatial resolution. This is due to the essentially different flow features arising from the adoption of the three-dimensional framework and is further investigated in the next section.

6.3. Comparison with experimental data

Comparisons with the experimental data from Saltari et al. (2022a) are firstly addressed by comparing the numerical results in terms of average and standard deviation of the energy dissipated per oscillation cycle, namely $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{diss}$ and $\sigma_{\mathcal{E}}$. The latter are available only for the experimental tests performed at $a_0 = 1.5g$ and $a_0 = 3.0g$ while for the rest of the test matrix only average values are available. In figure 11 the 2D and 3D SPH average and standard deviation of the dissipated energy per cycle are compared to their experimental counterpart.¹ For the cases at $a_0 = 1.5g$ a very good agreement, both in terms of average and standard deviation, is observed for most of the tested frequencies. The SPH results are characterised by slightly larger values of $\sigma_{\mathcal{E}}$ and, in particular, 2D results exhibit larger values than 3D ones. This feature is observed for all the test cases. However, for this value of a_0 no substantial differences are observed between 2D and 3D solutions. Note that for lower frequencies (that is, higher kinetic energy) the standard deviation is significantly larger as a consequence of the more pronounced chaotic character of

¹A sine sweep test is repeated ten times to evaluate the dispersion of the energy dissipated. Accordingly, 10 trends of dissipated energy as a function of the frequency per acceleration amplitude are employed to characterize the standard deviation as follows:

$$\sigma_{\mathcal{E}}^{(exp)}(\omega_0(t), a_0) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N_r} \sum_{k=1}^{N_r} \left(\mathcal{E}_{diss_k}^{(exp)}(\omega_0(t), a_0) - \bar{\mathcal{E}}_{diss}^{(exp)}(\omega_0(t), a_0) \right)^2}$$

where $N_r = 10$ is the number of repetition, $\mathcal{E}_{diss_k}^{(exp)}(\omega_0(t), a_0)$ and $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{diss}^{(exp)}(\omega_0(t), a_0)$ are, respectively, the experimental trend of the dissipated energy evaluated per acceleration amplitude of the k -th repetition and the mean trend.

Figure 11: Comparison between experimental results and SPH simulations of the average dissipated energy per cycle, \bar{E}_{diss} , for the cases at $a_0 = 1.5g$ (left) and $a_0 = 3.0g$ (right). Error bars are representative of the standard deviation $\sigma_{\mathcal{E}}$.

Figure 12: Vertical force acting on the tank as a function of the tank displacement: comparison between experimental results (left), 3D SPH (middle) and 2D SPH (right) for the case at $a_0 = 3.0g, f = 13Hz$.

the flow.

As for the cases at $a_0 = 3.0g$ (right plot of figure 11), characterised by larger energy content, much larger discrepancies between 2D and 3D solutions arise. Evidently, the 3D outcomes follow quite closely the experimental curve whereas the 2D one predict a different trend, resulting in a large underestimation of the dissipated energy for the case at the lowest frequency. Further, the standard

Figure 13: Vertical force acting on the tank as a function of time: comparison between experimental results (black), 3D SPH (red) and 2D SPH (blue) for the case at $a_0 = 3.0g$, $f = 13Hz$. The time considered in the experiment is centred with respect to the related sweep interval.

deviation of the 2D solution is significantly overpredicted whereas a fair agreement is found between the standard deviation measured in the experiments and in the 3D simulations.

Interestingly, the experimental data exhibits very small values of $\sigma_{\mathcal{E}}$ with respect to the cases at $a_0 = 1.5g$ although the kinetic energy of the flow is four times larger for the same frequency. At this nominal acceleration the time evolution of the flow is more close to a purely periodic evolution as it regularly impacts against the ceiling and the floor of the tank at each oscillation. On the contrary, in 2D solutions (bottom plots of figure 7) the distribution of the fluid is irregular and the impacts occur in a sparse fashion across the tank. This is reflected in a highly irregular evolution of the dissipated energy which is also the reason of the high values of $\sigma_{\mathcal{E}}$. The adoption of a 3D framework allows for recovering the regularity of the impacts as many more fluid jets are produced at each half-period (see figure 6), covering the whole ceiling surface.

The above observations can be appreciated also by looking at the hysteresis cycles of the vertical force acting on the tank. In figure 12 the vertical force is plotted as a function of the tank displacement for experiment, 3D and 2D SPH solutions. The experimental force F_z is obtained by applying a resampling at $640Hz$ with an antialiasing filter of the recorded force acting on the tank. The

force is normalised with respect to ma_0 . The numerical force has been treated in a similar way by applying a moving average filter at $640Hz$. It is worth noticing that the experimental load cells were not sensitive to the static component, *i.e.* the weight of the liquid, and therefore this component was subtracted in the numerical force. The 2D solution exhibits a quite noisy pattern, which is the result of the multiple impacts occurring in the flow. On the other hand the 3D solution is much smoother as the same impacts occur in the form of multiple quasi-cylindrical jets impinging against the ceiling and floor, a process which is repeated in an almost periodical fashion cycle after cycle. In figure 13 the same forces are plotted as a function of the non-dimensional time t/T . From this plot it is clear that the 2D solution systematically over-predict both positive and negative peaks with respect to the 3D solution and the experimental recordings.

A comprehensive picture of the overall agreement between the SPH predictions of the dissipated energy and the experiments is reported in figure 14. The different flow patterns and dissipative behaviours result in the need of describing dissipated energy as a function of acceleration and frequency. Indeed, at low acceleration values and high frequency the kinetic energy content is small and surface tension effects become relevant. Conversely, at high acceleration and low frequency the kinetic energy content is large and the flow essentially impacts twice per cycle against the tank horizontal walls. In this case surface tension is less important and flow damping is driven by impacts. It is worth to notice that, to better figure out the role of the vertical acceleration and excitation frequency, the energy dissipated per cycle by the fluid is expressed normalised with respect to mU^2 , that is two times the maximum kinetic energy stored by the fluid mass when *frozen*. $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{diss}/(mU^2)$ was also referred as the sloshing loss factor in Pizzoli et al. (2022). The domain of representation is the acceleration normalised by the gravity a_0/g and the nondimensional frequency $\omega_0/\sqrt{g/h}$. The scattered data of the non-dimensional dissipated energy predicted by the 2D and 3D SPH models are shown in the upper and lower plots, respectively, representing the degree of energy dissipated by the fluid through the marker colour. The scattered data are superimposed on the non-dimensional dissipated energy $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{diss}/(mU^2)$ contour map, obtained by interpolating the experimental data through the radial basis functions as in Saltari et al. (2022a). These two plots provide an idea of the capability of the SPH models to predict the energy dissipation in very different sloshing regimes.

The 2D SPH model (upper plot) is able to predict a level of dissipation of the same order of magnitude of the experimental one. However, a large underestimation (up to 25%) is observed for the cases characterised by accelerations higher or equal to $3g$ and frequencies lower than $12Hz$ ($\omega_0/\sqrt{g/h} < 4$). In fact, these

are the cases for which the kinetic energy is larger and, in this region, 3D effects become relevant. On the other hand, the 3D SPH model (lower plot) is able to return a level of dissipation that is notably close to the experimental one for all the considered fluid dynamics regimes. This result is in agreement with recent findings by Michel et al. (2022a) where 2D solutions underestimated with respect to 3D the dissipated energy for comparable flow conditions.

The magnitude of the difference of sloshing-induced dissipated energy between the experiments and the SPH models (blue for 2D and red for 3D) can be also appreciated by the scattered bar plot in figure 15. While the 3D model is able to maintain the error with respect to the reference experimental data always below the 15% (except for the points with $a_0 = 1.5g$ featured by low dissipation and higher variability, see left plot of figure 11), the 2D model under-predicts the level of dissipation at low frequency (up to 40%) while generally slightly over-predicting at higher frequencies.

Similarly to figure 14, figure 16 provides the comparison of the sloshing-effective mass fraction given by experimental data and the SPH model. It can be noticed that, while the 2D model poorly captures its trend in the frequency-amplitude domain, the 3D SPH model is able to well capture the trend of β over the considered domain although the numerical value is systematically smaller than its experimental counterpart. This difference is mainly due to the uncertainty in the measurement of tank solid and liquid mass inside the tank (small uncertainties in their estimation propagate into an overall bias in the estimation of β), but also to uncertainties in the method used to process the data to estimate the sloshing-effective mass fraction. It relies, indeed, on the evaluation of the Fourier transform of the signals in windows embedding few cycles, thus making its estimation affected by leakage and time-frequency resolution (more specifically, for the experimental data obtained by sine-sweep tests).

Conclusions

In the present work an enhanced SPH method was used to model the violent sloshing flow occurring in a tank subjected to vertical harmonic excitation. The recent experimental campaign performed by Saltari et al. (2022a) was taken as reference. A large number of test conditions were considered by varying excitation frequency and peak acceleration, focusing on cases where the flow is characterised by high fragmentation and violent impacts against the tank ceiling. With respect to previous studies of the same kind, in the present approach the sloshing dissipated

Figure 14: Comparison of the dissipated energy between experimental results and SPH model simulations (2D (top) and 3D (bottom) for the entire test-case matrix.

Figure 15: Percentage difference of dissipated energy between SPH models and experiments.

energy was measured by averaging over several oscillation cycles, thus allowing for robust numerical outcomes and a sound validation against experimental data.

Both 2D and 3D frameworks were considered. It was found that the former generally provides fair predictions of the dissipated energy for low-energy regimes (*i.e.* cases characterised by peak acceleration lower than $3g$ or frequency higher than $12Hz$) while underestimations up to 30% are observed in more violent cases. On the other hand, 3D simulations provided values of the dissipated energy within 10% of error for most of the cases considered. It is worth noting that 3D results were also close to the experimental reference also in terms of dispersion (standard deviation) over the periods when that information was available. The comparison with experimental data involved also the measured forces and more complex flow signatures such as the sloshing-effective mass fraction Saltari et al. (2022b). It is worth remarking that the numerical model adopted considered only the liquid phase, the air phase being neglected. The appropriateness of such a choice for the prediction of the energy dissipation in sloshing flows is in agreement with previous findings in Marrone et al. (2016b) and Bouscasse et al. (2014b).

Although the air phase was neglected, the introduction of surface tension model was found important for the accurate simulation of the flow during fragmentation and fluid impacts. This was particularly relevant in this study because of the

Figure 16: Comparison of the Sloshing-effective mass fraction β between experimental results and SPH simulations (2D (top) and 3D (bottom)) for the entire test-case matrix.

small size of the considered tank. The results of the present work represent the basis for adopting SPH numerical models for further studies of high-frequency vertical sloshing flows or, from an engineering standpoint, for providing numerical solutions to train Reduced Order Model solvers that can be integrated into dynamic wing response simulations as in Pizzoli et al. (2022); Saltari et al. (2022b).

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References

- Abramson, H., 1966. The dynamic behavior of liquids in moving containers. NASA SP-106. NASA Special Publication 106.
- Benjamin, T.B., Ursell, F.J., Taylor, G.I., 1954. The stability of the plane free surface of a liquid in vertical periodic motion. *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. Series A. Mathematical and Physical Sciences* 225, 505–515.
- Bouscasse, B., Colagrossi, A., Souto-Iglesias, A., Cercos-Pita, J., 2014a. Mechanical energy dissipation induced by sloshing and wave breaking in a fully coupled angular motion system. I. theoretical formulation and numerical investigation. *Physics of Fluids* 26, 033103.
- Bouscasse, B., Colagrossi, A., Souto-Iglesias, A., Cercos-Pita, J., 2014b. Mechanical energy dissipation induced by sloshing and wave breaking in a fully coupled angular motion system. II. experimental investigation. *Physics of Fluids* 26, 033104.
- Calderon-Sanchez, J., Martinez-Carrascal, J., Gonzalez-Gutierrez, L., Colagrossi, A., 2021. A global analysis of a coupled violent vertical sloshing problem using an sph methodology. *Engineering Applications of Computational Fluid Mechanics* 15, 865–888.
- Cercos-Pita, J., Antuono, M., Colagrossi, A., Souto-Iglesias, A., 2017. SPH energy conservation for fluid–solid interactions. *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering* 317, 771–791.

- Colagrossi, A., Landrini, M., 2003. Numerical simulation of interfacial flows by smoothed particle hydrodynamics. *Journal of computational physics* 191, 448–475.
- Constantin, L., De Courcy, J., Titurus, B., Rendall, T.C., Cooper, J., 2021. Analysis of damping from vertical sloshing in a sdof system. *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing* 152, 107452.
- De Courcy, J.J., Constantin, L., Titurus, B., Rendall, T., Cooper, J.E., 2021. Gust loads alleviation using sloshing fuel, in: *AIAA Scitech 2021 Forum*.
- Gambioli, F., Chamos, A., Jones, S., Guthrie, P., Webb, J., Levenhagen, J., Behruzi, P., Mastroddi, F., Malan, A., Longshaw, S., et al., 2020. Sloshing wing dynamics—project overview. *Proceedings of 8th Transport Research Arena TRA 2020, April 27-30, 2020, Helsinki, Finland*.
- Gambioli, F., Malan, A., 2017. Fuel loads in large civil airplanes, in: *International Forum on Aeroelasticity and Structural Dynamics IFASD 2017*.
- Gambioli, F., Usach, R.A., Kirby, J., Wilson, T., Behruzi, P., 2019. Experimental evaluation of fuel sloshing effects on wing dynamics, in: *International Forum on Aeroelasticity and Structural Dynamics*. Savannah, Georgia, USA, paper.
- Graham, E., Rodriguez, A., 1952. The characteristics of fuel motion which affect airplane dynamics. *Journal of Applied Mechanics* 19, 381–388.
- Loubère, R., Maire, P.H., Shashkov, M., Breil, J., Galera, S., 2010. Reale: a reconnection-based arbitrary-lagrangian–eulerian method. *Journal of Computational Physics* 229, 4724–4761.
- Marrone, S., Colagrossi, A., Calderon-Sanchez, J., Martinez-Carrascal, J., 2021a. Numerical study on the dissipation mechanisms in sloshing flows induced by violent and high-frequency accelerations. II. comparison against experimental data. *Phys. Rev. Fluids* 6, 114802. URL: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevFluids.6.114802>, doi:10.1103/PhysRevFluids.6.114802.
- Marrone, S., Colagrossi, A., Di Mascio, A., Le Touzé, D., 2015. Prediction of energy losses in water impacts using incompressible and weakly compressible models. *Journal of Fluids and Structures* 54, 802–822.

- Marrone, S., Colagrossi, A., Di Mascio, A., Le Touzé, D., 2016a. Analysis of free-surface flows through energy considerations: Single-phase versus two-phase modeling. *Physical Review E* 93, 053113.
- Marrone, S., Colagrossi, A., Di Mascio, A., Le Touzé, D., 2016b. Analysis of free-surface flows through energy considerations: Single-phase versus two-phase modeling. *Physical Review E* 93, 053113.
- Marrone, S., Colagrossi, A., Gambioli, F., González-Gutiérrez, L., 2021b. Numerical study on the dissipation mechanisms in sloshing flows induced by violent and high-frequency accelerations. I. theoretical formulation and numerical investigation. *Phys. Rev. Fluids* 6, 114801. URL: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevFluids.6.114801>, doi:10.1103/PhysRevFluids.6.114801.
- Marrone, S., Saltari, F., Michel, J., Mastroddi, F., 2022. Sph prediction of energy dissipation in a sloshing tank subjected to vertical harmonic excitations, in: 16th ERCOFTAC SPHERIC International Workshop, pp. 208–215.
- Martinez-Carrascal, J., González-Gutiérrez, L., 2021. Experimental study of the liquid damping effects on a sdof vertical sloshing tank. *Journal of Fluids and Structures* 100, 103172.
- Meringolo, D., Colagrossi, A., Marrone, S., Aristodemo, F., 2017. On the filtering of acoustic components in weakly-compressible SPH simulations. *Journal of Fluids and Structures* 70, 1–23.
- Michel, J., Antuono, M., Oger, G., Marrone, S., 2023. Energy balance in quasi-lagrangian riemann-based sph schemes. *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering* 410, 116015. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cma.2023.116015>.
- Michel, J., Durante, D., Colagrossi, A., Marrone, S., 2022a. Energy dissipation in violent three-dimensional sloshing flows induced by high-frequency vertical accelerations. *Physics of Fluids* 34, 102114.
- Michel, J., Vergnaud, A., Oger, G., Hermange, C., Le Touzé, D., 2022b. On Particle Shifting Techniques (PSTs): Analysis of existing laws and proposition of a convergent and multi-invariant law. *Journal of Computational Physics* , 110999doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcp.2022.110999>.

- Monaghan, J.J., Gingold, R.A., 1983. Shock simulation by the particle method sph. *Journal of computational physics* 52, 374–389.
- Pagliaroli, T., Gambioli, F., Saltari, F., Cooper, J., 2022. Proper orthogonal decomposition, dynamic mode decomposition, wavelet and cross wavelet analysis of a sloshing flow. *Journal of Fluids and Structures* 112, 103603. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfluidstructs.2022.103603>.
- Parshikov, A., Medin, S., 2002. Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics using inter-particle contact Algorithms. *Journal of computational physics* 180, 358–382.
- Perlin, M., Choi, W., Tian, Z., 2013. Breaking waves in deep and intermediate waters. *Annual review of fluid mechanics* 45, 115–145.
- Pizzoli, M., Saltari, F., Coppotelli, G. and Mastroddi, F., 2023. Neural network-based reduced-order modeling for nonlinear vertical sloshing with experimental validation. *Nonlinear Dynamics* .
- Pizzoli, M., Saltari, F., Mastroddi, F., Martinez-Carrascal, J., González-Gutiérrez, L.M., 2022. Nonlinear reduced-order model for vertical sloshing by employing neural networks. *Nonlinear dynamics* 107, 1469–1478.
- Saltari, F., Pizzoli, M., Coppotelli, G., Gambioli, F., Cooper, J.E., Mastroddi, F., 2022a. Experimental characterisation of sloshing tank dissipative behaviour in vertical harmonic excitation. *Journal of Fluids and Structures* 109, 103478.
- Saltari, F., Pizzoli, M., Gambioli, F., Jetzschmann, C., Mastroddi, F., 2022b. Sloshing reduced-order model based on neural networks for aeroelastic analyses. *Aerospace Science and Technology* , 107708doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ast.2022.107708>.
- Sun, P., Colagrossi, A., Marrone, S., Antuono, M., Zhang, A., 2019. A consistent approach to particle shifting in the δ -Plus-SPH model. *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering* 348, 912–934.
- Vergnaud, A., Oger, G., Le Touzé, D., DeLefte, M., Chiron, L., 2022. C-csf: Accurate, robust and efficient surface tension and contact angle models for single-phase flows using sph. *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering* 389, 114292. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0045782521005892>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cma.2021.114292>.

Wendland, H., 1995. Piecewise polynomial, positive definite and compactly supported radial functions of minimal degree. *Advances in Computational Mathematics* 4, 389–396. doi:10.1007/BF02123482.